

IMIDOCHLORIDES. PART VII. REACTION OF ANILIDE IMIDOCHLORIDES WITH ETHYL SODIOACETOACETATE. SYNTHESIS OF 4-HYDROXY-2-PHENYL-3-ACETYLQUINOLINES

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Benzanilide imidochloride has been condensed with ethyl sodioacetoacetate and the resulting intermediate condensation product, which could not be isolated in a pure state, has been cyclised to 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline. The synthesis has been extended to other imidochlorides derived from benzoyl derivatives of mono substituted anilines and the corresponding 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinolines, which are otherwise inaccessible, have now been synthesised. The synthesis has been also extended to naphthalene series and the corresponding benzoquinolines have been synthesised from imidochlorides derived from benzoyl derivatives of α - and β -naphthylamines.

In continuation of the previous work reported from this laboratory on the application of anilide imidochlorides to the syntheses of heterocyclic compounds (Shah and Heeramaneck, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 428; 1937, 867; Shah and Ichaporia, *ibid.*, 1936, 431), benzanilide imidochloride has been condensed with ethyl sodioacetoacetate. Ethyl sodiomalonate has been found to give with benzanilide imidochloride two products namely, ethyl mono- α -(phenyliminobenzyl)-malonate and ethyl di- α -(phenyliminobenzyl)-malonate, of which the former was found to undergo cyclisation yielding 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline (Just, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2623; 1886, 19, 983, 1462, 1545; Shah and Heeramaneck, *loc. cit.*). No work appears to have been done in the case of ethyl sodioacetoacetate which has now been studied.

The condensation of benzanilide imidochloride with ethyl sodioacetoacetate, when carried out in toluene, afforded an uncrystallisable intermediate condensation product namely, ethyl α -(phenyliminophenyl)-acetoacetate. The crude condensation product was then cyclised by heating under reduced pressure to obtain the hitherto unknown 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline (I).

The hydroxyquinoline structure has been assigned to the product from the analogy of synthesis of 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-carbethoxyquinoline from benzanilide imidochloride and ethyl sodiomalonate (Just, *loc. cit.*) and it finds support in the solubility of the product in dilute alkali and also in the formation of its functional derivatives like methyl ether, oxime, 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and hydrochloride, all of which have been prepared.

The method has been extended to various other substituted imidochlorides derived from benzoyl derivatives of mono-substituted anilines, viz., *o*-, *m*-, *p*-toluidines, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-chloroanilines, *p*-methoxy- and *p*-ethoxy-anilines, and the corresponding *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinolines, which are otherwise inaccessible, have now been synthesised in about 10% yield, calculated on the weight of imidochloride employed.

The condensation of benz-*m*-toluidide imidochloride afforded a product which appeared to be a mixture of *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5-methyl- and *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-7-methylquinolines from which only one isomer could be isolated in a pure state. In case of benz-*m*-chloroanilide imidochloride, a similar mixture obtained could not be separated into two components; however, their methyl ethers were separable as they differed considerably in their solubility in ethyl alcohol.

The above synthesis has been extended to the naphthalene series and the corresponding benzoquinolines, viz., *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylbenzo-7:8-quinoline (II) and *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylbenzo-5:6-quinoline (III) have been prepared from the imidochlorides derived from the benzoyl derivatives of α - and β -naphthylamines respectively. In case of benz- β -naphthalide imidochloride the cyclisation of the intermediate condensation product may theoretically lead to the angular compound (III) or the linear compound (IV). However, the quinoline derivative has been assigned the constitution (II) as β -naphthylamine is found to undergo ring-closure usually in α -position (Lellmann and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3154; von Braun and Gruber, *ibid.*, 1922, 55, 1710).

EXPERIMENTAL

Reaction of Benzanilide Imidochloride with Ethyl Sodiaoacetate: 4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline.—The solution of benzanilide imidochloride (11 g., 1 mol.) in anhydrous toluene was added to a suspension of ethyl sodiaoacetate prepared from sodium (1 g., 1 atom) and ethyl acetoacetate (11 g., 2 mols.) in toluene, and the reaction mixture refluxed, in absence of moisture, in an oil-bath at 120°-130° for 3 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was treated with water and extracted with ether. The ether, toluene and excess of ethyl acetoacetate were removed by distillation—the latter two under reduced pressure (30 mm.) and preferably below 130°. The condensation product, thus obtained as a viscous mass, did not solidify even at lower temperatures and resisted all attempts at crystallisation from different solvents.

For the purpose of ring-closure, the crude condensation product was heated under reduced pressure (30 mm.) in an oil-bath at 190°-200° till the evolution of bubbles from the reaction mixture ceased. The reaction mixture was then extracted a number of times with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and subsequent neutralisation of the alkaline extract by hydrochloric acid (the excess of which was avoided) afforded *4*-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline which crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale yellow needles (yield 2 g.), m.p. 282-84°. (Found: C, 77.9; H, 5.1; N, 5.0. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 77.5; H, 4.9; N, 5.3 per cent) The quinoline derivative is insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform and dissolves with slight difficulty in excess of hot methyl and ethyl alcohol. It dissolves in dilute solution of alkali giving yellow solution.

The methyl ether, prepared by dimethyl sulphate and alkali method in acetone, crys-

tallised from ethyl alcohol, m.p. 214-15°. (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* was prepared by passing dry hydrogen chloride in suspension of the quinoline in alcohol and isolated by diluting the reaction mixture with dry ether. (Found: Cl, 11.9. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N.HCl$ requires Cl, 12.1 per cent). It had no definite melting point but decomposed at high temperatures.

Oxime, m.p. 262°. (Found: N, 9.7. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.1 per cent). *2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone*, m.p. above 308°. (Found: N, 15.5. $C_{23}H_{17}O_8N_5$ requires N, 15.8 per cent) (with Mr. S. A. Kulkarni).

The following compounds were prepared by the same method described above and cyclisation was generally effected by heating under reduced pressure (30 mm.) in an oil-bath at about 200°. The quinolines were sparingly soluble substances and were crystallised from ethyl alcohol, except where mentioned. The yields of the quinoline derivatives are calculated on the weight of the imidochloride employed. The methyl ethers and hydrochlorides were prepared by the same method described above. Hydrochlorides had no definite melting point, but decomposed at high temperatures.

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-8-methylquinoline was prepared from benz-*o*-toluidide imidochloride (9.5% yield), m.p. 215°. (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. 94-95° (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{19}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 11.3. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N.HCl$ requires Cl, 11.4 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5- or 7-methylquinoline was prepared from benz-*m*-toluidide imidochloride and obtained as a mixture on crystallisation of the crude product from ethyl acetate, m.p. 220°-240°, and afforded one isomer in pure state, when crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 277-80°. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. 199°-202° (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{19}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 11.7. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N.HCl$, requires Cl, 11.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-6-methylquinoline was prepared from benz-*p*-toluidide imidochloride in 9.5% yield, m.p. 255° (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. 137° (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{19}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 11.2. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N.HCl$ requires Cl, 11.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-8-chloroquinoline was prepared from benz-*o*-chloroanilide imidochloride as yellow needles from acetic acid, m.p. 284-86°, yield 12%. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.7 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. 101° (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{18}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 10.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2NCl.HCl$ requires Cl of HCl, 10.9 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5- or 7-chloroquinoline was prepared from benz-*m*-chloroanilide imidochloride, and obtained as a mixture, m.p. 292°-300° (7.5% yield). (Found: N, 4.8. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.7 per cent). It afforded two *methyl ethers*, one soluble in alcohol and crystallised from the same, m.p. 205°-10° (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.5 per cent); and one sparingly soluble in alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 247-50° (analysis not done due to lack of the material).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-6-chloroquinoline was prepared from benz-*p*-chloroanilide imidochloride and crystallised from acetic acid as yellow needles, m.p. 298-300°,

12.5% yield. (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.7 per cent). *Methyl ether* prisms, m.p. 225° (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 11.6. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2NCl.HCl$ requires Cl of HCl, 10.9 per cent).

Benz-p-anisidide imidochloride was prepared from benz-*p*-anisidide (50 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (50 g.) at $220^\circ/10$ mm. (Found: Cl, 14.4. $C_{14}H_{12}ONCl$ requires Cl, 14.8 per cent). It is soluble in common organic solvents like benzene, ether, etc. It was characterised by the preparation of anidine by Shah's modified method (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1925, 7, 219). The imidochloride (2 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of freshly distilled aniline (2 g.) and diethylaniline (6 g.) and the whole heated at $120^\circ-130^\circ$ for 3 hours in absence of moisture. Treatment of the cooled reaction mixture with dilute hydrochloric acid afforded a sparingly soluble hydrochloride which on trituration with ammonia and alcohol gave *N-p-methoxyphenyl-N'-phenylbenzamide* (yield 1 g.), crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 120° . (Found: N, 9.1. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_2$ requires N, 9.2 per cent). *Hydrochloride* prepared from the base and hydrochloric acid in glacial acetic acid melted at 158° . (Found: Cl, 10.5. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_2.HCl$ requires Cl of HCl, 10.7 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline (12% yield) from benz-*p*-anisidide imidochloride crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 270° (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent). *Methyl ether*, prismatic needles, m.p. 203° (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 10.7. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3N.HCl$ requires Cl of HCl, 11.0 per cent).

Benz-p-phenitidide imidochloride was prepared from benz-*p*-phenitidide (50 g.) and phosphorus pentachloride (50 g.) and it distilled at $260^\circ/10$ mm. (Found: Cl, 13.7. $C_{18}H_{14}ONCl$ requires Cl, 14.0 per cent). *N-p-Ethoxyphenyl-N'-phenylbenzamide*, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol in fine prisms, m.p. 142° . (Found: N, 9.0. $C_{21}H_{20}ON_2$ requires N, 8.0 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-6-ethoxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline (12% yield) from benz-*p*-phenitidide imidochloride, crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 295° (Found: N, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. 205° (Found: N, 4.2. $C_{20}H_{19}O_3N$ requires N, 4.4 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 10.7. $C_{19}H_{17}O_3N.HCl$ requires Cl, 10.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylbenzo-7:8-quinoline (5.5% yield) was prepared from benz- α -naphthalide imidochloride (which distilled at $245^\circ/10$ mm.), m.p. $263-65^\circ$. (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. $139-40^\circ$ (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 4.3 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylbenzo-5:6-quinoline (8.8% yield) was prepared from benz- β -naphthalide imidochloride, m.p. $262-64^\circ$. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). *Methyl ether*, m.p. $219-220^\circ$ (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{22}H_{17}O_2N_2$ requires N, 4.3 per cent). *Hydrochloride* (Found: Cl, 10.1. $C_{21}H_{16}O_2N.HCl$ requires Cl, 10.4 per cent).

The authors are grateful to the Chemical Society for a research grant for this investigation.